

Application of a system-level approach to the design of steel structures

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ABSTRACT

Design of steel structures according to Eurocode is currently performed by a two-step approach, where structural analysis is followed by design checks on each individual structural element. In this approach, the resistance of a structural system is determined by a single member that first reaches its capacity. However, the redundancy of a structure allows redistribution of forces after a member fails, which means that as a system, the structure has additional load-bearing capacity. This capacity is exploited in the recently introduced direct design method (DDM), which determines the resistance of the entire structural system through advanced structural analysis. While the framework of the DDM seemingly enables more efficient use of material, it is not clear how the method compares with the governing member-based design approach of the Eurocode.

This study quantifies the efficiency of the DDM in terms of material consumption compared to the conventional two-step design approach. Trussed plane frames with hollow section members are designed for minimum weight employing the DDM and EN 1993 separately. These structures are widely used in the Nordic countries as main frames of hall-like buildings, and they possess redundancy to enable redistribution of internal forces. Therefore, they provide an interesting application for demonstrating the practical use of the DDM, with analysis of the benefits and challenges of the method.

Results of numerical case study show that the DDM can achieve at least a material saving of 6.6 % compared to the conventional two-step design approach. This leads to a more economical use of steel, as well as a reduced environmental impact. The material savings can be further increased by considering the rotational stiffness of the joints, which is also illustrated in the case study.

Keywords: direct design method, GMNIA, cold-formed hollow sections, structural system safety

1 INTRODUCTION

Direct Design Method (DDM) is a recent system-level approach to the design of steel structures (1–3). In the DDM, design verification is done for the entire structure by performing geometrically and materially nonlinear analysis with imperfections (GMNIA). This type of analysis allows to fully exploit material plasticity and redundancy of the structure. Considering the structure, e.g. a frame, as a system in the design means that there is no need for checking the resistance of individual member. This is the main difference and benefit of DDM relative to the conventional design approach of Eurocode 3 (4). Moreover, the GMNIA employed in the DDM provides the designer insight on the behaviour and failure modes of the structural system. Exploiting the full load-bearing capacity of the structure as a system can lead to more economical use of steel, as well as reduced environmental impact.

Since its introduction, the direct design method has been studied and developed e.g. for frames consisting of hot-rolled I profiles (1, 2, 5) and cold-formed tubes (3, 6), and as well as for roof trusses and portal frames made of cold-formed high-strength structural hollow sections (7, 8). The main task in applying the DDM on a family of structures is to determine the corresponding system

safety factor (1–3, 5–8). This requires reliability analysis, where statistical distributions of various geometrical and material properties are employed. Determining the system safety factor also entails choosing the appropriate value of the reliability index, and this has to be considered on a system-level.

This article explores the advantages of the direct design method compared to the Eurocode EN 1993-1-1 (4) design method in tubular structures. In this study, a trussed portal frame, which is commonly used in Nordic countries, is designed using both the direct design method and the conventional design method of EN 1993-1-1 (4). The frame structure consists of cold-formed square and rectangular tube profiles made of S700 material. The structure, consisting of several structural elements and joints, is a clear single structural system with redundancy and a redistribution of loads, as well as the possibility of exploiting the plasticity of the material. In this study, the differences in design results and profiles of frames when the structure is designed by the conventional Eurocode method and by the direct design method are compared. The masses of the frames, which are designed by different methods, are determined by the profile selections and member lengths of the frames. The potential material savings of DDM can be estimated using this information.

In this study, the frame structure is designed with DDM using fully rigid and hinged joints. The buckling resistances of members were calculated according to the boundary conditions of the structural model in DDM, unlike the conventional design method that uses standard EN 1993 instructions (4) to determine the buckling resistance of members based on buckling lengths. When the stiffness of the joints is unknown and there is no suitable joint model, the effect of the joints on the dimensioning results is estimated by modelling the joints of the truss as fully rigid and hinged for non-linear structural analyses. Although the assumption of fully rigid joints in the truss is overconservative, it allows to estimate the greatest potential that could be achieved by considering joints in structural analyses.

2 DESIGN PROCESS WITH DDM

Applying the DDM to structural design can be described by the following steps.

Step 1: The design process begins with making an initial guess of the system configuration. This involves determining the layout and geometry of the structure, as well as member profiles and materials.

Step 2: Nominal FEM models are created for the structure. The nominal models are used to determine the resistance of the structure. Pre-defined nonlinear material model (9) that includes residual stresses (10), and local (bow) and global (sway) geometric imperfections are incorporated in the models. Several nominal models with varying member bow imperfections are generated to ensure a load-bearing capacity that complies with the reliability level according to the design standards and to find the lowest nominal resistance. Both in-plane and out-of-plane bow imperfections are considered. In this study, 50 FEM nominal models are prepared per load combination. In 25 models, in-plane bow imperfections are applied, and in the other 25 models, the bow imperfections are out-of-plane. For bow imperfections, a sinusoidal half-wave is used as the shape with amplitude $L/1000$, where L is the length of the member, as is suggested in prEN 1993-1-14 (11). Sway imperfections are defined according to EN 1993-1-1 (4) and modelled as equivalent horizontal loads acting at the top ends of the columns. *Fig. 1* illustrates different combinations of in-plane bow imperfections at 50-fold magnification.

Step 3: Nonlinear analysis of the nominal models is performed. During the analysis, loads are increased with load factor α , and the output is the ultimate load factor, α_u , which corresponds to the failure of the structure. The ultimate load factor also provides the nominal resistance of the entire structural system for the respective nominal model. The smallest ultimate load factor among the nominal models, $\alpha_d = \min\{\alpha_{u,1}, \alpha_{u,2}, \dots, \alpha_{u,n}\}$, where n is the number of nominal models, determines the resistance for the given load combination.

The ultimate load factor α_u of the structure is the peak value of the load-displacement curve. Alternatively the α_u is taken as the load factor corresponding to the situation where the stiffness of the structure is reduced to 5 % of the initial value (3).

Step 4: Design verification for the structural system is done. The only design check in the DDM is the criterion of *Eq. (1)*, which states that the design is feasible, if the design load factor is greater than equal to the system safety factor γ_{ADM} . If this criterion is not met, the profiles of the structural system are updated based on an analysis of the calculation results and the process returns to step 2. The closer the design load factor α_d gets to the system safety factor γ_{ADM} , the more efficiently the material of the structure is utilized.

$$\alpha_d \geq \gamma_{ADM} \quad (1)$$

The system safety factor $\gamma_{ADM} = 1.15$ is applied in this study for the trussed portal frame. This value is based on reliability studies carried out in earlier research (8), and it corresponds to reliability index 3.04.

Fig. 1. Examples of in-plane bow imperfections for two nominal models at a 50-fold magnification.

3 DESIGN OF A TRUSSED PORTAL FRAME

Consider the trussed portal frame depicted in *Fig. 2*. The structure is designed in this study by the direct design method according to the design process of Section 2 and by the conventional design approach of Eurocode 3 (4). The frame has a span of $L_s = 28$ m and column heights of $H_c = 9$ m. The height of the truss at the mid-span and at the supports is $H_m = 2,8$ m and $H_s = 2,3$ m, respectively. The roof slope is 1:30. The frame is symmetrical with respect to the mid-span.

In the conventional Eurocode design method, the stiffness of welded joints is accounted for by reducing the buckling lengths of the web members to 75 % of their system lengths, even though the joints to the chords are hinged in the structural model. In the direct design method, the concept of buckling length is not used, but buckling is included in the structural analysis, where the stiffness of the joints is taken into account according to the structural model.

In this study, the joints of the truss are modeled as hinges for the design according to the Eurocode. When applying the DDM, two cases are considered: i) truss with hinged joints; and ii) truss with rigid joints. The purpose is to explore the impact of the rotational stiffness of the joints on the design. The hinged and rigid joints represent the extremes in rotational stiffness. Consequently, this comparison quantifies the range of attainable advantage by the DDM when the stiffness of the joints is considered.

Fig. 2. Geometry, loads, and supports of the frame, with the global coordinate system.

3.1 Loads

In addition to self-weight, the structure is subject to permanent loads $G_k = 0,5 \text{ kN/m}^2$, snow loads of $Q_{k,snow} = 2,0 \text{ kN/m}^2$, and wind loads of $Q_{k,wind} = 0,64 \text{ kN/m}^2$. The values of the variable loads have been determined according to the standards EN 1991-1-3 (12) and EN 1991-4+AC+A1 (13) and the Finnish national annex (14).

Four load combinations according to EN 1990+A1+AC formula 6.10 (15) are considered in design:

$$LC_1 = \gamma_G \cdot G_k + \gamma_Q \cdot Q_{k,snow} \quad (2)$$

$$LC_2 = \gamma_G \cdot G_k + \gamma_Q \cdot Q_{k,snow} + \gamma_Q \cdot \Psi_{0,A} \cdot Q_{k,wind} \quad (3)$$

$$LC_3 = \gamma_G \cdot G_k + \gamma_Q \cdot Q_{k,wind} \quad (4)$$

$$LC_4 = \gamma_G \cdot G_k + \gamma_Q \cdot Q_{k,wind} + \gamma_Q \cdot \Psi_{0,A} \cdot Q_{k,snow} \quad (5)$$

where $\gamma_G = 1,35$ and $\gamma_Q = 1,5$ are the partial factors for permanent and variable actions, respectively, and $\Psi_{0,A}$ is the factor for the combination value of a variable action. $\Psi_{0,A} = 0,6$ for wind load when the snow load is a leading action, and $\Psi_{0,A} = 0,7$ for snow load when the wind load is a leading action.

3.2 Member profiles

Square and rectangular hollow sections S700MH steel are employed for the members. The cross-sections of the members belong to Class 1 or 2 (4), and the non-dimensional slenderness $\bar{\lambda}$ of the members is limited to a value of 3.0 (4). As a geometrical condition, it is required that the profile width of the braces cannot exceed the width of the chord profiles. However, the range of validity for welded joints between RHS brace and chord members according to EN 1993-1-8 (16) is not considered.

For both design approaches, the lightest feasible profiles from a given catalogue are determined by simple manual exploration.

3.3 Design

The frame is designed by the DDM according to the steps defined in Section 2, employing the criterion of Eq. (1). Recall that the system safety factor $\gamma_{ADM} = 1,15$.

In the design according to Eurocode 3, the buckling length of the brace members in-plane and out-of-plane is 75 % of the length of the brace members. The in-plane buckling length of the chords is 90 % of the distance between consecutive joints, i.e. 90 % of the lengths of TC₁, TC₂, BC₁, BC₂, etc. (*Fig. 2*). It is assumed, that out-of-plane buckling of the top chord is prevented, and the out-of-plane buckling length of the bottom chord is the system length, i.e., the length of the bottom chord. Since the bottom chord is mainly subjected to tensile stress, its buckling is not decisive in the load combinations considered.

The buckling lengths of the columns are defined through linear buckling analysis of the frame. For the in-plane buckling lengths, the smallest eigenvalue corresponding to a sway mode, α_{cr} (4), is employed. The out-of-plane buckling lengths are based on the smallest eigenvalue corresponding to out-of-plane column buckling without the requirement of sway mode. For both buckling directions, the load combination LC₂ of *Eq. (3)* yields the smallest eigenvalue. These eigenvalues are used for the other load combinations as well, even though the buckling length factors are actually load combination-specific.

Resistance of members is checked according to the EN 1993-1-1 (4), including cross-section verifications and, for members in compression, buckling resistance. For combined bending and axial compression, Method 2 of EN 1993-1-1 is employed (Annex B of (4)).

3.4 Structural modelling and analysis

This section presents the basics of structural models and analyses for both design methods. The design of frame structures is based on the structural models and analyses presented in this section.

3.4.1 Direct design method

Finite element analyses are carried out by the Abaqus software (17). Members are modelled using beam elements (B31) with arbitrary cross-section definition to account for the rounded corners of square and rectangular hollow sections. Each chord segment (TC₁, TC₂, BC₁, BC₂, etc. in *Fig. 2*) between two joints is divided into 16 beam elements. The columns are composed of 51 elements. Near the joints, the length of the elements is about 100 mm, and elsewhere the element length is approximately 200 mm.

The end nodes of the braces are connected to the chord surfaces. The resulting eccentricity with respect to the centre line of the chord is modelled by using Abaqus “beam” type multipoint constraint. Hinged brace-to-chord and chord-to-column connections were modelled by releasing rotational degrees of freedom (DOF) for both in-plane and out-of-plane rotations.

In the nominal models of the direct design method, bow imperfections are considered independently in both the XZ- and YZ-planes by modelling them to the geometry. Sway imperfections are considered only in the XZ-plane and are accounted for by applying equivalent horizontal loads to the columns.

The stress-strain curve of the material is modelled using the Effective Material Model (EMM), which includes the effect of residual stresses and corner strength enhancements in the beam element-based nonlinear analysis (9). Additionally, the material model considers the von Mises yield condition and associated plastic flow with isotropic hardening. The arc-length method with force-controlled loading is used in the structural analysis.

3.4.2 EN 1993 design method

For the design according to Eurocode, geometrically nonlinear second-order analysis with linear elastic material model is performed. Member bow imperfections are not included in the structural models, because the corresponding second-order effects are considered in the buckling design rules of EN 1993-1-1. Global initial sway imperfections, however, are taken into account and their effect is modelled as additional horizontal forces according to the standard EN 1993-1-1 (4). On average, the members are divided into 16 Timoshenko beam elements with average length of 200 mm.

The upper ends of the columns and top chords transition out of the plane are prevented. All joints of the truss are hinged, including the chord-to-column joints. The top chord joint at the apex is rigid.

4 DESIGN RESULTS BY DDM AND ACCORDING TO EUROCODE

This section presents profiles of the frame's members and masses of the frames with different design methods when the frame is designed according to section 3. Additionally, differences in design results are presented when the structure is designed with the DDM and the conventional Eurocode method. Furthermore, the catalogue utilized in the profile selection is for the material grade S420 and here also employed for S700 (18), which affects the profile choices.

4.1 Minimum weight designs

Table 1 presents the minimum weight profiles when the frame is designed by the conventional Eurocode method according to EN 1993-1-1 (4) and by the DDM according to Sections 2 and 3 with hinged and rigid connections. The height h , width b , and wall thickness t ($h \times b \times t$) of the rectangular hollow sections are in millimetres (Table 1). The names of the members are presented in Fig. 2. Additionally, Table 1 presents the relative mass differences of each member of the entire frame, calculated as

$$m_{d1} = \frac{m_{DDM, hinged} - m_{EC3}}{m_{EC3}} \quad (6)$$

$$m_{d2} = \frac{m_{DDM, rigid} - m_{EC3}}{m_{EC3}} \quad (7)$$

where $m_{DDM, hinged}$ and $m_{DDM, rigid}$ are the masses of the member or frame obtained by DDM with hinged and rigid truss joints, respectively, and m_{EC3} is the mass of the member or frame by design according to Eurocode (4).

Table 1. Designed frames by conventional method and DDM with hinged and rigid truss joints in which $\gamma_{ADM} = 1.15$. Mass differences are calculated by Eq. (6)–(7).

Member	EN 1993-1-1 (max. utilization [%])	DDM		Mass difference [%]	
		Hinged joints (max. utilization acc. EN 1993-1-1 [%])	DDM Rigid joints	m_{d1}	m_{d2}
Column*	200x120x8.8 (90 %)	180x120x8 (105 %)	180x120x8	-14.4	-14.4
Top chord*	150x100x8.8 (100 %)	150x100x8 (109 %)	150x100x7.1	-7.7	-17.0
Bottom chord	100x80x4 (87 %)	100x80x4 (87 %)	90x50x5	0.0	-7.6
Brace B1*	100x100x4 (71 %)	100x100x5 (59 %)	80x80x4	23.1	-21.2
Brace B2	60x60x3 (72 %)	60x60x3 (72 %)	60x60x3	0.0	0.0
Brace B3*	100x100x4 (51 %)	100x100x4 (52 %)	80x80x4	0.0	-21.2
Brace B4	60x60x3 (38 %)	60x60x3 (38 %)	60x60x3	0.0	0.0
Brace B5*	80x80x4 (57 %)	90x90x4 (42 %)	60x60x5	13.9	-11.8
Brace B6	60x60x3 (7 %)	60x60x3 (6 %)	60x60x3	0.0	0.0
Brace B7*	60x60x3 (40 %)	60x60x3 (39 %)	60x60x3	0.0	0.0
Total mass	2163 kg	2019 kg	1862 kg	-6.6	-13.9

* The normal force of the member is compression.

The first observation from Table 1 is that, for the braces in tension, (B2, B4, and B6), identical profiles are obtained by DDM and Eurocode. With hinged truss joints, the DDM enables smaller column and top chord profiles, corresponding to 14.4 % and 7.7 % weight reduction. On the other

hand, DDM required larger compression braces B1 and B5, being 23.1 % and 13.9 % heavier, respectively, than their counterparts provided by the design according to EN 1993-1-1. In total, the DDM yields a weight reduction of 6.6 % compared to the design obtained by Eurocode.

If the brace-to-chord and chord-to-column joints are considered rigid, the benefits of DDM become more pronounced. In this case, all compressed braces except B7 -which is under small axial force- are smaller with DDM. Moreover, the top chord can be reduced even further from the case with hinged truss joints, as well as the profile of the bottom chord. The total weight reduction amounts to 13.9 % in favour of the DDM.

The proportion of columns, top chords, bottom chord, and braces (14 pieces per truss) in the total mass is on average 32.1 %, 38.0 %, 14.1 %, and 15.8 %, respectively. This illustrates that the greatest savings in mass can be achieved by reducing the size of columns and top chord.

The differences seen in the compressed members by the design methods are likely due to differences in buckling capacities. The conventional method applies a constant buckling length, which are approximations of the real buckling lengths. For example, the buckling lengths of the brace members are 75 % of the brace length (4). This takes into account the rotational stiffness of the welded hollow section joints, although they are modelled as hinged. DDM considers buckling implicitly in the analysis, and then it is crucial to model the stiffness of the connection appropriately. If the brace-to-chord joints are modelled as hinges, the DDM cannot utilize the stiffness of the joints which they possess. In these cases, the buckling length allowed by the Eurocode yields favourable results. This can be seen in heavier brace members (B1 and B5) for the case with hinged brace-to-chord joints in the DDM.

From the above, it can be deduced that the stiffness of the truss joints plays an important role in the overall performance of the DDM and it should be considered in the structural model. The weight reduction obtainable by the DDM ranges from 6,6 % (hinged truss joints) to 13,9 % (rigid truss joints). With actual joint stiffnesses, the weight saving lies somewhere between these values, and although the results hold for a single frame only, it provides enough motivation for further studies. It should also be noted that, in addition to stiffness, the resistance of the joints needs to be incorporated into the structural analysis associated with the DDM.

4.2 Structural behaviour and failure modes of the frame

Efficiency of design according to Eurocode can be assessed by examining the utilization ratio of members, i.e. the ratio of effect of actions to the corresponding resistance. These values are given in parentheses in *Table 1*. It can be seen that the utilization ratio of the columns and chords is close to 100 %, and it is quite high for the most loaded braces as well (about 70 %). It can be deduced that the top chord is the most critical member, and structure is likely to fail by beam-column instability of the top chord. For all members except brace B6, the maximum utilization ratio is obtained in load combination LC₂, i.e. with leading snow load.

The DDM does not provide utilization ratios for individual members. The overall utilization of material in the frame can be assessed by comparing the minimum design load factor among the load combinations with the system safety factor $\gamma_{ADM} = 1,15$. The minimum design load factor is $\alpha_d = 1,18$, obtained for the load combination LC₂. The system utilization ratio is the $\gamma_{ADM}/\alpha_d = 1,15/1,18 = 0,9745 = 97,5 \%$, which indicates very efficient use of material.

For further insight on the relationship between the designs by the two approaches, the minimum weight solution by the DDM for the case with hinged truss joints is designed according to EN 1993-1-1, and the member utilization ratios are given in *Table 1*. Interestingly, the utilization ratio of the column and top chord exceed 100 %, meaning that these members would be infeasible according to the Eurocode. This highlights the benefits of using advanced analysis in system-level design: allowing redistribution of forces and considering instabilities in analysis enables to employ the full load-bearing capacity of the structure with the same level of safety as in the conventional design approach.

One of the strengths of the DDM is that advanced analysis provides detailed insight on the behaviour of the structure until failure as a system. *Fig. 3* shows the load-displacement curves of the decisive nominal models for load combinations LC_1 - LC_2 (Eq. (2)-(3)) and LC_3 - LC_4 (Eq. (4)-(5)) from point A of the frame (*Fig. 2*) with “DDM hinged joints” profiles of *Table 1*. The deformations of the frame are in the negative Z-direction for load combinations LC_1 and LC_2 in *Fig. 3a* and in the positive X-direction for load combinations LC_3 and LC_4 in *Fig. 3b*.

Fig. 3. Load-displacement curves for point A a) in the negative Z-direction from the load combination LC_1 and LC_2 ; b) in positive X-direction from the load combination LC_3 and LC_4 .

The failure modes of the frame in each load combination can be determined by exploring the deformations, and stresses and strains of the structure during loading. Such analysis reveals that in LC_1 the structure fails by the buckling of the top chord at the design load factor. Similarly, in LC_2 , out-of-plane buckling of columns is the governing failure mode. Plastification of the fixed end of the left column results in failure in LC_3 . For LC_4 , excessive deformations and yielding lead to failure. The decisive load combination for the considered frame by the DDM is LC_2 , which has the lowest nominal model load factor $\alpha_d = 1,18 > \gamma_{ADM} = 1,15$.

Fig. 4 shows the von Mises stresses of the decisive nominal model (resulting to lowest resistance) in LC_2 in the ZX-plane at the moment when the first member attains the nominal strength of 700 MPa. This occurs when the load factor $\alpha = 1.08$. The first yielding members are the bottom chord of the truss, and the right-hand side column, and they begin to yield almost at the same load step. The frame is also subject to in-plane sway deformations. The loss of load-carrying capacity is caused by the out-of-plane buckling of columns, as shown in *Fig. 5* when the design load factor $\alpha_d = 1.18$ is achieved. *Fig. 5* also depicts the equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) of the structure to illustrate the inelastic deformations (17). If the PEEQ value is greater than zero, the material is yielding (17). *Fig. 5* shows that positive PEEQ values can be seen at several locations of the structure which indicates that redistribution of forces has been activated. The equivalent plastic strain is approximately 3.3 ‰ at the bottom chords, about 3.1 ‰ at the base of the right column, and 2.8 ‰ at the joint of the bottom chord and column. However, the out-of-plane buckling of the columns is the cause of the final collapse of the structure, and therefore the load-displacement curve (*Fig. 3a*), curve LC_2 drops abruptly.

Fig. 4. The von Mises stresses of the nominal model LC₂ at first yield in the bottom chord and right-hand side column.

Fig. 5. In-plane (left) and out-of-plane (right) deformations and plastic strains of the nominal model LC₂ with 10-fold magnification from the calculation results when the design load factor $\alpha_d = 1.18$ is reached.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the practical use of the direct design method and quantifies its potential material savings for a high-strength steel tubular trussed frame structure often employed in the Nordic countries (albeit usually with regular steel). Contemporary structural analysis software can treat geometrically and materially nonlinear analysis of such frames with moderate effort. Introducing the local geometrical imperfections for the members is arguably the most laborious task in modelling, but this can be automated by appropriate software tools.

The numerical example presented in the paper illustrates the benefits of advanced analysis and system-level approach on the economy of the design and for better understanding of the failure modes. It was demonstrated that the stiffness of the truss joints plays a significant role in the outcome and should be considered in the structural model. With nominally pinned joints, the DDM provided 6,6 % lighter design than the conventional Eurocode member-based approach, and this saving amounted to 13,9 % when the truss joints were modelled as rigid. In practice, brace-to-chord joints are likely to be semi-rigid, which means that their stiffness should be evaluated appropriately. Additionally, the resistance of the joints needs to be incorporated in the structural model.

For the DDM to be adopted in practice, the key element is the definition of the system safety factor. This must be done separately for each family of structures following commonly accepted reliability procedures. A related item for discussion is the required reliability index for structural systems. This value has a significant impact on the system safety factor, which again directly influences the possible benefits of the DDM compared to the conventional design approach.

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